

Accommodation

Codes

Name	Description	Files	References
Proposals for future pandemics or health crises	What suggestions do residents have for upcoming pandemics/health crises in order to receive better information and assistance?	0	0
Other measures that are needed	What other measures are needed if there is a new crisis or pandemic?	20	40
Adaptation and communication	Residents' suggestions on how to adapt communication and information in preparation for future pandemics/health crises in order to obtain better information and effective assistance.	19	50
Verbal information.		12	25
Social challenges in specific areas	What measures are needed if a new crisis or pandemic occurs in specific areas? What challenges exist and what needs to be improved?	9	18
Continue with HI	The residents' proposal is that HI should continue.	5	5
Collaborate with other organisations	Residents suggest that collaboration with other organisations is needed.	7	22
Language	Language is important and a necessary tool for residents to be able to understand information correctly.	0	0

Name	Description	Files	References
Information provided in one's own language	What measures are needed if there is a new crisis or pandemic, including providing information in their own language?	15	24
The difference between different sources in different languages varies	How can it vary between different sources in different languages and what differences are there?	24	57
The role of language in understanding	Language can undermine health information through the spread of misinformation, unclear communication, and misleading advice.	13	27
Understanding and learning about COVID-19 and vaccination	This theme concerns how informants have tried to understand information about the pandemic, difficulties, the importance of language, and the significance of cultural factors.	0	0
Understanding COVID	What understanding do residents have of COVID-19 and how do they relate to it?	0	0
Background and role of understanding		3	5
Explanatory models	What explanatory models did residents think or see during the pandemic?	16	36
Anxiety, fear	Residents feel fear and anxiety about both COVID-19 and the COVID-19 vaccine.	13	30
Do not believe in COVID-19	Residents do not believe in COVID-19	6	7

Name	Description	Files	References
Was it difficult to find information?	Was there anything in the information about COVID-19 that was difficult to understand? Let's go back to the pandemic itself.	10	19
Change in knowledge and worldview regarding COVID-19 for the interviewees living in the area	Change in knowledge and views on COVID-19 among residents interviewed in the area.	0	0
How residents in the area changed their knowledge and worldview regarding COVID-19 during the pandemic	How residents in the area changed their knowledge and views on COVID-19 during the pandemic.	9	11
Language	Language is important and a tool that is needed for residents to be able to understand information correctly.	0	0
Information provided in one's own language	What measures are needed if there is a new crisis or pandemic, including providing information in their own language?	15	24
The difference between different sources in different languages varies	How can it vary between different sources in different languages, and what differences are there?	24	57
The role of language in destruction	Language can destroy health information through the spread of misinformation, unclear communication, and misleading advice.	12	24
What caused the interviewee's own knowledge and worldview of COVID-19 to change	What caused the interviewed resident to change their knowledge and view of COVID-19.	7	8

Name	Description	Files	References
What information did the residents consider to be the most important?	What information did the residents consider to be the most important?	6	8
What prevented the residents' knowledge and worldview of COVID-19 from developing	What prevented the residents' understanding and view of COVID-19 from developing.	8	14
In the beginning	How did the beginning of the pandemic affect the residents' understanding and views of COVID-19?	6	15
Sources of information about COVID-19 and vaccination that the interviewed residents received	Sources of information about COVID-19 and vaccination that the interviewed resident received	0	0
Other		18	44
From work		8	12
Misinformation and various conspiracy theories	Misinformation and various conspiracy theories among residents about COVID-19 and vaccinations.	11	19
From the media	Media as sources of information about COVID-19 and vaccination that the interviewed residents had received	1	1
From the internet and social media		19	3

Name	Description	Files	References
Television and radio	Various sources of news	18	27
From the authorities	The authorities were used as sources of information about COVID-19 and vaccinations that the residents interviewed had access to.	19	35
COVID-19 helpline	The COVID-19 helpline was used as a source of information about COVID-19 and vaccinations that was accessible to the residents interviewed.	12	16
HI	HI was the source of information about Covid-19 and vaccinations that the residents interviewed had access to.	13	14
Opinion on information received	Residents' opinions about the information provided during the pandemic about COVID-19 and vaccinations.	11	19
Trust in information	What factors influence residents' trust in information, what do they believe, what do they not believe, and what needs to be done to build trust?	0	0
Background and trust	How do background factors influence trust in information among residents?	1	1
RELIGION		3	5
What is needed to build trust	What needs to be done to build trust among residents?	18	39
Who is not trusted	Who do residents not trust?	13	22
Vaccines	Vaccines that affect trust?	6	28

Name	Description	Files	References
Who do people trust?	Who do residents trust?	10	36
Opinions on the actions of the authorities	What were the opinions of the residents interviewed about the actions of the authorities?	0	0
Other	What other opinions did the residents interviewed have about the actions of the authorities?	5	5
Need more action	According to the residents interviewed, what did the authorities fail to do?	11	26
Lack of information		9	20
Receipt of information from authorities		0	0
How the interviewed residents received information about COVID-19 from the authorities		2	3
Resistance and questioning of information from authorities by the interviewed resident		3	4
Opinions about the information		14	3
Appreciation	According to the residents interviewed, what did the authorities do well?	12	15